

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF PHARMACIST-LED INTERVENTIONS ON CHRONIC DISEASE MANAGEMENT: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Received: May 04, 2025

Accepted: Jun 04, 2025

Published: Jun 06, 2025

Abstract

Background:

The role of pharmacists has evolved from a product-oriented practice to a more clinical, patient-centered approach. Pharmacist-led interventions have shown potential in managing chronic diseases, which require long-term medication adherence and continuous patient education.

Objective:

This systematic review aims to evaluate the impact of pharmacist-led initiatives on the management of chronic diseases by synthesizing recent research on clinical outcomes, medication adherence, and healthcare costs.

Methods:

A comprehensive literature search was conducted in PubMed, EMBASE, Scopus, and Web of Science using terms related to “Pharmacist Intervention” and “Chronic Disease Management.” Studies published between January 2010 and December 2024 were screened in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. Inclusion criteria focused on studies with pharmacist-led interventions reporting outcomes such as clinical parameters (e.g., HbA1c, blood pressure), medication adherence, and patient satisfaction. A total of 30 studies met the criteria for final analysis.

Results:

Pharmacist interventions demonstrated a positive impact across a variety of chronic conditions, including diabetes, hypertension, asthma, and COPD. These interventions, such as medication reviews, patient counseling, and follow-up support, improved clinical outcomes, medication adherence, and inhaler techniques. In cardiovascular care, pharmacist involvement post-discharge reduced medication discontinuation and potential rehospitalization. Several studies also indicated potential healthcare cost savings. However, variability in study design and outcome measures introduced heterogeneity.

Conclusion:

Pharmacist-led interventions significantly contribute to the effective management of chronic diseases by enhancing adherence, improving clinical outcomes, and potentially reducing healthcare expenditures. Future efforts should focus on addressing implementation barriers, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and evaluating long-term economic impacts to fully integrate pharmacists into chronic care models.

Key words: *Chronic disease, Pharmacist, Systematic review*

1 INTRODUCTION:

Pharmacy is now suitably positioned to change from a task-and product-oriented (dispensing) to a clinical field of patient oriented (providing care, counsel, and guidance).¹ Community pharmacies provide healthcare for minor illnesses to millions of people worldwide every day. Because of their presumed low cost and availability, pharmacists are often the first line of contact within the healthcare system in developed nations as well as underdeveloped ones.² Studies reveal that roughly half of those with long-term conditions do not follow their prescribed regimens of medication.³ According to a 2014 report from the American Heart Association, 24% of patients among patients with admitted for a heart attack, 34% did not take their prescriptions within seven days

of discharge from the hospital. Myocardial infarction ceased taking one of their prescribed drugs within 30 days of hospital discharge.⁴ In addition to having greater rates of morbidity and death, patients who ignore their prescriptions squander a significant amount of money for the healthcare system.⁵ Pharmacists are essential when it comes to treating long-term illnesses including diabetes, high blood pressure, COPD, asthma, and others. Pharmacists play a vital role in helping patients with chronic illnesses take their prescription drugs as directed. Patients' self-management of diabetes, a chronic illness, depends on a number of factors.⁶ There is mounting evidence that suboptimal glycaemic control can be caused by poor medication adherence, lifestyle choices, and a lack of knowledge about diabetes.^{7,8} Patients need to be knowledgeable about their condition and have the ability to make decisions in order to prevent complications and practise effective self-care and disease management.^{9,10} Pharmacists working in clinical settings might be one method to provide patients with information about diseases. Pharmacists are essential in helping patients learn how to manage their medications, food, and self-care.¹¹ Patients with COPD and asthma are mostly treated with inhaled medications.¹² Although appropriately administering inhalation medication might be challenging for many patients, it is necessary for both a favourable clinical response and the efficient pulmonary disposition of medications.¹³ Pharmacy care services have been shown in recent research to improve pulmonary patients' inhalation technique and improve medication adherence and health outcomes.¹⁴ The goal of this systematic analysis is to assess how pharmacist-led programs affect chronic disease management. This review will highlight by integrating current research results the possible role these treatments might play in enhancing healthcare delivery and patient results.

2 METHODS:

2.1 SEARCH STRATEGY

To discover every article that has been written regarding treating chronic illnesses and pharmacist involvement, a comprehensive study of the literature was conducted. To discover every article that has been written regarding treating chronic illnesses and pharmacist involvement, a comprehensive study of the literature was conducted. Four databases were searched using the phrases ["Pharmacist Intervention"] AND ["Chronic Disease Management"]: Web of Science, EMBASE, Scopus, and PubMed. Searches were conducted using Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) words on PubMed and Embase Subject Headings (Emtree) terms on EMBASE. The articles were chosen in agreement under the PRISMA guidelines for Meta-Analysis and Systematic Reviews

2.2 STUDY SELECTION:

2.2.1 INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- ✓ Study that includes pharmacist-led approaches to managing chronic illnesses, as well as peer-reviewed studies or systematic reviews that have been published in reliable databases.
- ✓ Clinical parameters (e.g., blood pressure, HbA1c), medication adherence, and medical expenses are among the reported outcomes.
- ✓ We include both experimental studies (randomised controlled trials, non-randomized trials) and observational research (cross-sectional, case-control, cohort).
- ✓ Only English-language publications were considered in the search. Only research publications published between January 2010 and December 2024 were included.

2.2.2 EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- ✓ Research involving pregnant women, animals as models, and children under the age of eighteen were not included, nor were letters to the editor, opinion article, lead articles, case reports, or case series.
- ✓ Studies that are purely theoretical or do not rely on empirical evidence ought to be disregarded.

2.3 DATA EXTRACTION

The names of the authors, the year of publication, the disease, the demographic characteristics, the chemist intervention, and the outcome measures included all the pertinent information needed for the systematic review extracted. Two authors (D.P. and A.S.) checked the extracted data for any discrepancies, and those that were found were settled by debate and agreement. Intervention outcomes such as medication adherence, patient satisfaction, and patient outcome were of interest.

2.4 DATA ANALYSIS

Every study had a narrative description. If comparable outcome data from two or more trials were available, the data were combined. We expected that methodological and clinical heterogeneity would likely exist and impact

the outcome, thus we employed the random effect meta-analysis model in the meta-analysis. A single pairwise comparison was created by combining similar data investigations with several arms. For continuous outcomes, the results are shown as mean differences with a 95% confidence interval.

2.6 STUDY PROTOCOL REGISTRATION

The study protocol was registered with PROSPERO (CRD420251011931).

Figure.1 PRISMA FLOWCHART

3 RESULTS

3.1 STUDY CHARACTERISTICS

61 of the 83 articles that were found underwent further review. On the basis of the exclusion criteria, 18 items were eliminated. The relevance of forty-three articles and papers was assessed. Seven studies had results that were irrelevant, while six publications had inadequate data and unclear methods. The total number of articles was thirty. (Figure.1)

YEAR	STUDY TYPE	DISEASE	POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS	PHARMACIST INTERVENTION	ASSESSMENT	OUTCOME
<i>Shadi Farsaei et al</i> (2011)	randomized controlled trial	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	172 people with uncontrolled type 2 diabetes were selected, and they were split into two groups at random: the intervention group and the control group.	Patients in the intervention participated in two instructional sessions about adherence and anti-hyperglycemic medications. They were given a pill box and diabetes diary to keep track of their exercise, sick days, medication, and blood sugar levels.	Anti-hyperglycemic medications were explained to patients by the Pharmacist, who also covered their classifications, doses, mechanisms, efficacy, safety, interactions, and storage. Adherence, its function in managing diabetes, and methods to enhance adherence and self-care were discussed in a second session.	Relative to the control group, patients in the group receiving intervention had noticeably lower average HbA1c and fasting blood sugar three months of follow-up.
<i>Aileen R Neilson et al</i> (2015)	pilot randomized controlled trial	Patient with chronic Pain and receiving prescribed painkillers on a regular basis (defined as getting two or more prescriptions in the last 120 days) acute	Of the 196 patients, One:one:one randomized patients to Get TAU (n=63). pharmacist medication	Treatment as usual (TAU), pharmacist medication review with feedback to the general practitioner, or pharmacist	At baseline and on the three- and self report was utilized for six month follow-up to	For chronic pain, pharmacist-led therapies appear to be more costly and provide QALYs that are

		prescriptions for analgesics and/or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), as well as one recurring prescription	review + pharmacist prescribing (n=70); either pharmacist review alone (n=63).	medication review with in-person pharmacist prescription were the two groups to which patients were randomly assigned.	evaluate the summary scores in mental (SF-12 MCS) and physical (SF-12 PCS).	equivalent to TAU.
<i>Ee Pin Chow et.al (2015)</i>	non-clinical randomised controlled trial	Diabetes Mellitus	Two groups of 150 patients were randomly allocated, including 75 individuals in each arm.	Knowledge of diabetes and adherence to treatment.	The 8-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale and the 14-item Michigan Diabetes Knowledge Test	A home-based intervention led by pharmacists can markedly raise diabetes 2 patient's awareness about their situation and pharmacological adherence.
<i>Jay M Patel et.al (2015)</i>	Cohort study	metastatic castrate-resistant prostate cancer	Thirty-one patients fulfilled the screening requirements and were eligible to participate. There were 14 patients in the pre-program implementation group and 17 patients in the post-program implementation group.	Providing drug information (DI), addressing drug interactions for the entire medication list, managing adverse events, addressing non-compliance, monitoring recommended lab parameters, adjusting the therapy of any medication (e.g., adding or discontinuing, changing the dose or interval), as well as (4) figuring out when chemotherapy should begin and end are all examples of a pharmacist's intervention.	After the patient progress notes were examined, the following data was extracted: Interventions made by the oncology chemist include (1) age, gender, race, insurance type, and encounter kind.	The typical count of measures laboratory parameter post-program Still, the general amount of time spent in therapy by the two groups was unchanged substantially.
<i>Tyler J et.al (2015)</i>	cross-sectional study	Diabetes and cardiovascular disease	128 study participants	Participants in the program are required to see a clinical pharmacist once a month for three months, after which they must see them every two months. Medication reviews, education, goal-	Three distinct groups of 17 modified statements from the Diabetes Disease State Management Questionnaire (DDSM-Q)	Patient satisfaction supports the adoption of DSM programs run by pharmacists.

				setting, vitals, and therapy modifications are all part of the visit. Once steady and informed, the frequency of visits is reduced to every three to six months.		
<i>Jeannine S. Skinner et.al</i> (2015)	retrospective case-control design	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	One hundred patients with type 2 diabetes (fifty MTM patients and fifty non-MTM patients).	In addition to reviewing the patient's T2DM prescription schedule, the Pharmacist gave verbal instruction and training on drug distribution, the optimum places to administer it, and health-promoting practices (diet, exercise, and quitting smoking). In order to verify comprehension, patients were asked to "teach back" the information.	The refill of anti-diabetes prescriptions was used to measure medication adherence.	Relative to the non MTM group, the stayed elevated. The MTM group's A1C and LDL readings too less than those of the non-MTM group.
<i>Javedh Shareef et al</i> (2016)	prospective randomized educational interventional study	Diabetes Mellitus	The experiment was completed by 106 patients in total, 55 in the intervention group and 51 in the control group.	Pharmaceutical care for patients in the intervention group included information about the condition and its symptoms as well as recommendations for dietary, exercise, and other lifestyle adjustments, while the control group did not get any pharmaceutical care until the end of the trial.	The researcher created a comprehensive diabetes mellitus knowledge questionnaire with 30 questions that address the many facets of diabetes.	The results indicated which the intervention relative to the group regular care group.
<i>John J. Ko et al</i> (2016)	retrospective study adopted a quasi-	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	One hundred fifty persons where 75 matched conventional	MMP patients met a pharmacist monthly. The first 60-minute visit	Not mentioned in the study	Patients of MMP saw a larger drop in average A1c

)	experimental design		medicine patients therapies grounded in baseline, age, gender, physical comorbidity insulin usage, A1c. Of these, seventy patients been enrolled in the pharmacist-led MMP.	assessed therapy needs and set A1c goals. Follow-ups included 20-minute diabetes education on therapy goals, self-monitoring, and glucometer use.		between two and baseline years beyond -1.24 vs. standard care patients P = 0.009; 0.59. The A1c for MMP patients was much less in relation to control subjects (8.06 versus 8.67, P = 0.014). Seemingly, A1c varied one year for MMP patients contrasted against control persons.
<i>Ejaz Cheema et al (2017)</i>	cross-sectional study	Hypertension, Diabetes, Asthma, COPD and antiplatelet/anticoagulants.	285 patients (160 female and 125 male)	Interventions included drug-related assessments of adherence and issues, plus non-drug counselling on nutrition, weight, alcohol, tobacco, exercise, and sexual health by chemists.	The pharmaceutical services negotiating committee (PSNC) created a verified set of worksheets for chemists to use the NMS in practice, and a 12-item questionnaire was taken from them.	According to this study, the NMS offers a chance to enhance the identification of side effects and prevent patients from misusing medications.
<i>Tim Langran et al (2017)</i>	prospective cohort study	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	5910 individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	Pharmacists evaluated 5910 patients and collaborated with general practice teams to optimize medication, recommend lifestyle changes, and schedule any of the nine essential care processes that the patients lacked, as suggested by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE).	Nine essential care processes suggested by NICE	The percentage of patients getting all nine of the NICE-recommended care procedures rose from 46% at the beginning of the trial in April 2013 to 58% at the end of the project in April 2014. Furthermore, more patients met their TC, BP, and HbA1c goals (from 78% to 82%,

						70% to 76%, and 65% to 70%, respectively). Statistics from Slough CCG's Quality Outcomes Framework (QOF) April 2013 to April 2014 shows the Improvement HbA1c, BP, and TC attained values drop in the year following finishing of the project.
Daniel A. ERK U et.al (2017)	prospective randomized controlled study	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	127 individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	The clinical pharmacist reviewed the patient's medication schedule and provided customized training and instruction on how to take their medications, including dosage, frequency, and additional safety precautions. They also provided information on smoking cessation, eating a balanced diet, and exercising regularly. During the trial period, the pharmacist attempted to alleviate patients' concerns regarding the use of their medicines and provided free telephone counseling.	Due to its affordability, simplicity, and ease of use, the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8) was employed to assess self-reported medication adherence.	Medication adherence improved noticeably and statistically significantly from baseline to three and six months for the intervention group compared to the control group (from 9.2% at baseline to 61% at six months).
<i>Eylem Ilktac</i>	Randomized	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	Of the 152 individuals, 75	The study pharmacist	The SDSCA questionnaire	The intervention patients' A1c

<i>Korcegez et al</i> (2017)	Controlled study		under a type 2 diabetes were in the group receiving intervention, and 77 were in the usual range. care group.	provided each patient with a fresh pamphlet at each visit and talked about the importance of self-monitoring blood glucose (SMBG), exercising, eating a balanced diet, and stopping smoking. The pamphlets included type 2 diabetes, its effects, medications, treatment goals, and self-care (e.g., SMBG, healthy eating, and exercise).	e is a well investigated and validated tool for assessing patients' self-care routines. It was translated into Turkish and validated on date 24. The Morisky-Green test was used to assess medication adherence at baseline and at the 12-month follow-up (validated and translated into Turkish).	readings decreased more than those of the usual care patients at the conclusion of the 12-month research period (-0.74% vs. -0.04%; P < 0.001). Between the beginning and the conclusion of the 12-month period, both groups' fasting blood glucose levels significantly decreased; nevertheless, there was no statistically significant difference between them.
<i>RossT et.al</i> (2016)	Multicenter Randomized Controlled Trial	Cardiovascular risk Patients	723 cardiovascular risk patients (370 intervention group and 353 usual care group)	Both internal and external reviewers assessed the online training course that the research team developed. Casefinding, cardiovascular risk assessment, chronic kidney disease, hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes, quitting smoking, controlling one's diet and lifestyle, and recording care plans for Alberta Health reimbursement are among the topics covered in the training curriculum.	Medication Therapy Management review	People in the intervention group had better results. Their systolic blood pressure improved. Their glycosylated hemoglobin levels went down. Their low-density lipoprotein cholesterol also decreased. Plus, more people in this group quit smoking.

<i>McNicholl IR et. al (2017)</i>	Prospective, randomized, interventional trial.	HIV-positive Patients	2700 HIV-positive Patients	By reviewing and reconciling prescriptions, a One Pharmacist with HIV credentials evaluated indications, patient usage, adherence, and adverse events using pill counts, interviews, and pharmacy data. Charts were updated in accordance with proven clinical indications.	Pharmacists play an important role in helping older patients with HIV. They check for potentially inappropriate prescribing, also known as PIP. To do this, they use two tools: the Beers criteria and the STOPP tool. These tools help pharmacists identify medications that may not be safe for older adults. By using these tools, pharmacists can ensure that patients receive the best care possible.	According to the results, focussing on those who use eleven or more chronic drugs would have the biggest impact and yield. Many PIP were found during a pharmacist-led examination of pharmaceutical prescription using the Beers and STOPP criteria; many of them may be addressed right away by a clinical pharmacist.
<i>Karen L. Margolis et.al(2018)</i>	A Cluster Randomized Clinical Trial	Uncontrolled Hypertension	The telemonitoring intervention group had 228 individuals, whereas the usual care group included 222 people. A total of 450 patients were randomized at random.	Telemonitoring-based blood pressure management system	The telemonitoring intervention group's participants received an automatic oscillometric blood pressure monitor for use at home, which recorded and sent their readings to a secure internet platform run by AMC Health.	The intensive intervention showed enduring effects lasting up to 24 months, including a year after the intervention ended. Sustaining long-term blood pressure control may require ongoing monitoring and restarting the intervention if blood pressure levels increase.

<i>Suhaj Abdul salim et.al(2018)</i>	A randomized controlled study	COPD	The researchers divided the 260 study participants into two groups. One group was called the Intervention Group (IG). The other group was called the Control Group (CG). The researchers assigned participants to these groups randomly. This means everyone had an equal chance of being in either group.	Medication adherence	The Medication Adherence Questionnaire, or MAQ, was created by Morisky, Green, and Levine. It helps to measure how well people stick to their medication plans. In the intervention group, a pharmacist led the strategy. This approach focused on several important points. First, it highlighted the importance of quick follow-up appointments. Second, it encouraged regular exercise. Third, it taught correct inhaler techniques. Fourth, it promoted quitting smoking. Lastly, it emphasized the need for medication compliance.	Improving patient self-efficacy through self-management education and shared decision-making can enhance adherence, improve outcomes, and reduce the economic burden of COPD. In resource-limited countries like India, involving non-physician healthcare professionals such as pharmacists may be a more effective strategy, as the current physician-centric model often lacks focus on patient education and counseling.
<i>Amanda W. Benedict et.al(2018)</i>	Retrospective cohort study	Diabetes Mellitus	The study comprised 15,903 participants, with 2,946 in the Complete Care	Efforts focused on improving medication adherence, ensuring	The efficacy of the intervention in enhancing patient care	Clinical pharmacists' management of type 2 diabetes led to larger

018)			Program (CCP) group and 10,859 in the Usual Care (UC) group.	prescription refills, administering vaccinations, addressing overdue health screenings, and reinforcing lifestyle education related to diabetes, hypertension, and dyslipidemia.	was assessed using HEDIS measures as standards.	decreases in A1c at 3 and 6 months, faster attainment of the HEDIS A1c objective of less than 8.0 percent, and more patients reaching this goal than those receiving conventional care.
<i>Martín Schulz et.al(2019)</i>	Prospective multicentre, randomized controlled study	Chronic heart failure	We randomly assigned patients to two different groups. One group had 127 patients, and we called it the normal care group. The other group had 110 patients, and we called it the intervention group.	Medication adherence, Proportion of patients who maintained adherence.	The study used the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe categorization system. Participants accessed this system through a secure online tool. They were randomly split into two groups. One group received pharmacy care, and the other group received usual care. This randomization was done in a 1:1 ratio, meaning each group had the same number of participants.	Pharmacy care significantly increased quality of life and adherence to heart failure medicines.
<i>Andrés Torres-Robles et.al(2021)</i>	Randomised controlled trial	Hypertension, Asthma, COPD	1038 patients	The control group continued their usual treatment. The intervention group got extra help to stick to their medication. This support was different from	A pharmacist's interview using the MGL MAQ tool to evaluate how effectively	Asthma, COPD, and hypertension patients' health outcomes and medication adherence were greatly enhanced by a

				what the control group experienced.	patients take their prescription drugs for hypertension, COPD, or asthma. Blood pressure readings, the results of the Clinical COPD Questionnaire (CCQ), and the Asthma Control Questionnaire (ACQ) are important markers for tracking and treating hypertension, COPD, and asthma.	community pharmacist-led intervention. Future studies have to concentrate on how to include these treatments into routine clinical procedures.
<i>Rasaq Adisa et.al (2024)</i>	quasi-experimental study	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and asthma	The study included two groups of patients. One group was called the control group, and it had 65 people. The other group was the intervention group, and it also had 65 people. Each group had a specific purpose in the study.	The intervention group received a follow-up educational and/or cognitive-behavioral intervention for two months, while the control group was provided normal care.	The baseline questionnaire asked important questions about COPD and asthma. It used two tests: the COPD Assessment Test (CAT) and the Asthma Control Test (ACT). These tests helped check how well patients were sticking to their medication plans. They also looked at how patients used their inhalers, like Diskus and	Pharmacists can make a big difference in managing asthma and COPD. They led interventions that helped patients control their asthma better. These efforts also reduced the impact of COPD. Patients in the intervention group followed their medication plans more closely. They used their inhalers more effectively compared to those in the control group. This shows how important it is for pharmacists to be involved

					<p>pressurized metered-dose inhalers (pMDIs). Finally, the questionnaire measured how well patients were controlling their asthma and COPD using a special scale called the Comprehensive Medication Adherence Assessment Scale (CMAAS12). This scale was created by the study's co-investigators.</p>	<p>in treating patients with chronic lung diseases. Their active role can lead to better health outcomes in clinical settings.</p>
<p><i>Ashlyn Aguiniga et.al(2024)</i></p>	<p>Retrospective study</p>	<p>Type 2 diabetes</p>	<p>61 patients in all.</p>	<p>CCM program</p>	<p>The North Texas Regional Institutional Review Board reviewed the research design. They decided it was exempt from certain regulations. The study followed important guidelines. These guidelines are called EQUATOR and STROBE. EQUATOR helps improve the quality and transparency of health research. STROBE</p>	<p>Clinical and cost gains are demonstrated for a medically complicated patient population with type 2 diabetes (T2D) when a collaborative, interprofessional Chronic Care Management (CCM) program is implemented in a single-center family practice lab. The report points out that its limitations include a limited sample size and the COVID-19 epidemic starting during the study period. It is recommended that future</p>

					focuses on better reporting of observational studies in epidemiology. Both sets of criteria ensure the research is reliable and clear.	studies investigate how interprofessional CCM programs affect health equality, comprehensive care management, and the transition from fee-for-service to value-based care.
<i>Manisha Jham et.al(2024)</i>	A Cluster Randomized Clinical Trial	Chronic Kidney Disease	A total of 1,596 patients joined the trial. Out of these, 842 patients were put in the control group. The other 754 patients were placed in the intervention group. This setup helped researchers compare the two groups effectively.	Medication management and education on chronic kidney disease (CKD).	Management of Population Health using Electronic Health Records.	This study found that patients with moderate-to-high-risk chronic kidney disease (CKD) who got a comprehensive community health management intervention powered by electronic health records were on angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors or angiotensin receptor blockers for longer periods of time. In comparison to standard treatment, this strategy did not, however, significantly delay the course of CKD or improve blood pressure management.
<i>Charles Worrell et.al (2024)</i>	Retrospective, quasi-experimental analysis	Hypertension, Cholesterol, Diabetes Mellitus.	10,477 patients	Clinical pharmacist-led medication adherence program: A pharmacist-led program using AI and pharmacy	Artificial Intelligence, Stellus Rx, Medicare Star ratings.	Through the use of technology and patient involvement, this pharmacist-led clinical service enhanced

				data identified high-risk patients, addressed medication gaps through coordinated care, and improved disease management, Medicare Star ratings, and overall healthcare cost savings.		medication adherence among people with long-term illnesses, leading to better disease management and notable cost savings.
<i>Sanaa Mekkad et.al (2024)</i>	Prospective randomized study	Diabetes Mellitus, Cardiac Conditions	500 patients in one group received treatment overseen by clinical pharmacists, whereas 500 patients in the other group received routine care without pharmacist intervention.	Medication management, Patient Education, Management of risk factors.	The clinical pharmacist's intervention was accompanied by the collection of baseline data, which included measurements of fasting blood glucose (FBG), glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), and the frequency of hypoglycemic episodes. Measurements of these indicators, especially HbA1c, were taken again after the intervention to evaluate any changes.	Clinical pharmacists play an important role in managing diabetes in hospitalized patients with cardiac problems as essential members of a multidisciplinary team. Their treatments are superior to conventional care alone in reducing fasting blood glucose (FBG) and HbA1c levels.
<i>Alexander J. Blood et.al(2024)</i>	Cohort study	Hypertension, Type 2 diabetes mellitus	The group with type 2 diabetes consisted of 125 individuals, whereas the group with hypertension consisted of 43 people.	To assist the clinical pharmacist, a group of remote retail pharmacists developed algorithms for managing chronic diseases based on clinical recommendations to help with drug	Changes in hemoglobin A1c, systolic BP, and diastolic BP were measured from the pre-index to post-index period	The pharmacist-managed group showed significant decreases in hemoglobin A1c and systolic blood pressure compared to matched controls. The potential

				management choices.		advantages of including pharmacists into value-based primary care settings to enhance the treatment of chronic illnesses linked to increased morbidity and mortality are demonstrated by these findings.
<i>Shorog M Altawalbeh et.al(2025)</i>	Prospective interventional study	Chronic kidney disease	142 patients	cost-benefit evaluation	Reconciliation of medications, The net benefit is calculated by subtracting the service charge from the total benefits, which include cost avoidance and savings. To do the base case computations, Excel software was utilized.	In Jordan, a typical low- and middle-income nation, the implementation of a supplemental medication reconciliation service by clinical pharmacists for patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) turns out to be cost-effective from a healthcare standpoint. This research emphasizes how important clinical pharmacists are to interdisciplinary healthcare teams.
<i>Roheena Zafar et.al(2025)</i>	A randomized controlled trial	Chronic kidney disease	A total of 100 patients were recruited in the trial; 50 were split between the intervention and control groups.	Drug related problems	Clinical pharmacists found drug-related problems at the start of the study. They used the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe (PCNE) 9.1	Quality of life (QoL) and laboratory indicators significantly improved in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) after clinical pharmacist-led treatments. Even though the suggested

					standards to identify these issues. To assess patients' quality of life, researchers used the Functional Assessment of Non-Life-Threatening Conditions (FANLTC) questionnaire. They evaluated the patients at both the beginning and the end of the research. This helped them see how patients' lives changed over time.	interventions were successfully carried out from the beginning to the conclusion, a significant percentage of them were neither approved nor carried out.
<i>Muhammad Rehan Sarwar et.al(2025)</i>	A research conducted before and after the intervention	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	81 participants	Evaluated the impact of a TT-focused HMR guided by a certified pharmacist on enhancing the health of people with COPD.	Evaluation of Respiratory Issues and Collaborative Community Care for Adult Long-term Smokers (RADICALS)	Health outcomes for those with COPD improved as a result of HMRs that targeted TTs. Primary care certified pharmacists can work with general practitioners to improve the management of COPD.
<i>Nur Burcu Kutluay et.al (2025)</i>	Prospective cohort study	Diabetes Mellitus	A total of 145 people were studied. Among them, 79 had diabetes. The remaining 66 had prediabetes.	The first appointment included a record of the patient's demographics, medical issues, test results, and waist circumference. The IPQ-R and knowledge questions were used to assess patient	The first appointment included a record of the patient's demographics, medical issues, test results, and waist circumference. The IPQ-R and knowledge	The study showed important improvements in several health measures. These included weight, waist size, blood sugar levels, cholesterol, HbA1c, and HOMA-IR readings. These changes

				understanding, while self-reports and medical records were used to document the patient's history of diabetes.	questions were used to assess patient understanding, while self-reports and medical records were used to document the patient's history of diabetes.	happened over a 90-day period, both before and after the pharmacist helped. Additionally, there were noticeable differences between the DMG group and the pDG group. This was true for their IPQ-R, DKMQ, and PKMQ ratings.
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4 DISCUSSION

This study looked at how pharmacists help manage chronic diseases. It found that pharmacists play a key role in patient-centered care. This is especially true for patients with chronic illnesses like asthma, diabetes, hypertension, and COPD.

Pharmacists do more than just give out medications. They are also involved in caring for patients. Many people see pharmacists first because they are easy to reach. This is especially important in community areas or places with limited healthcare options. Pharmacists are in a good position to implement treatments that increase drug adherence, educate patients about diseases, and improve health outcomes because of their accessibility.

The management of chronic diseases has highlighted poor drug adherence as a major problem, contributing to higher rates of morbidity, death, and medical expenses. Pharmacist-led treatments, including medication reviews, patient counselling, adherence monitoring, and education sessions, were repeatedly shown to significantly increase adherence rates across a range of chronic illnesses in the evaluated trials. For instance, greater glycaemic control was achieved in diabetes care when chemists were included, most likely as a result of better patient education and lifestyle counselling.

Pharmacist-supported discharge planning and follow-up has also been shown to considerably lower medication drop-off rates after hospitalisation in the setting of cardiovascular disease. This is crucial since stopping medicine too soon after a significant cardiac event, such as a myocardial infarction, might have negative effects and raise the risk of readmissions to the hospital.

Additionally, Pharmacist are critical in the management of respiratory conditions including asthma and COPD, where proper inhaler usage is necessary for successful therapy. Numerous studies that were included of this evaluation showed that when Pharmacists conducted customised instruction and demonstration sessions, inhaler practices, patient confidence, and overall disease management improved.

In addition to clinical results, economic assessments of the evaluated studies suggested that, in some healthcare systems, chemist treatments might save money by lowering avoidable complications and hospital stays.

It is important to recognise certain limits even in light of the positive data. The design, types of interventions, and outcome measures of several of the included studies differed, introducing heterogeneity and making it more difficult to conduct a more thorough meta-analysis.

Taking into account the obstacles that Pharmacists have while embracing more extensive clinical responsibilities is also crucial. These include the necessity for further training in certain fields, legislative restrictions, poor reimbursement models, and a lack of multidisciplinary collaboration. In order to more methodically integrate

pharmacist-led care models inside health systems, several obstacles must be removed.

To sum up, this study emphasises how important and beneficial chemists may be in the treatment of chronic illnesses. Improved clinical outcomes, better drug adherence, and possible cost savings are all linked to pharmacist-led initiatives. As the pharmacy field continues to develop into a more patient-centered field, healthcare systems ought to take use of Pharmacists' special position and abilities to enhance the treatment of chronic illnesses and the provision of healthcare in general.

5 CONCLUSION

This systematic study emphasises how important Pharmacists are becoming to the treatment of chronic illnesses. Interventions led by chemists have demonstrated a great deal of promise in enhancing health outcomes as the pharmacy profession develops into a more clinical and patient-centered field. Clinical metrics including blood pressure and glycaemic management are optimised, medication adherence is improved, and patient satisfaction and education are improved by Pharmacists, according to the reviewed data.

Because of their accessibility and frequent patient contact, pharmacists may close gaps in the treatment of patients with chronic illnesses by offering individualized counseling, ensuring proper medication administration, and encouraging self-management. In addition to improving patient outcomes, these measures may save healthcare expenditures by reducing complications and lowering readmissions to hospitals.

Although the study's heterogeneity has certain limits, the overall results are in favour of incorporating pharmacist-led care models into methods for managing chronic illnesses. Addressing implementation issues, encouraging multidisciplinary cooperation, and assessing the interventions' long-term viability and economic viability should be the main goals of future initiatives. Global advancement of patient-centered healthcare delivery may be significantly aided by strengthening the role of chemists in chronic care.

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